

ACCELERATED DURABILITY ASSESSMENT OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

The paper will describe how the accelerated durability assessment of composite materials and structures can be performed using the combination of two innovative methods; the accelerated testing methodology (ATM) and the strain invariant failure theory (SIFT). ATM is based on the time-temperature superposition principle, and is a systematic and efficient method of predicting the long-term durability of polymeric composite materials from series of simple tests performed at elevated temperatures. This method will be used to generate the material durability database, which can be used for the design of composite structure based on a new composite failure analysis method, SIFT. SIFT is a unique failure theory developed by the Boeing Company with the goal of improving the accuracy of the static strength prediction of complex composite structures. SIFT relates the basic materials properties to the strength of wide range of composite structures through elaborate finite element analysis. The advantages of combining these two methods are that SIFT can expand the applicability of the material durability database to wide range of composite structures, and that it can lead to significant reduction in the number of required durability tests. Also envisioned possible through the combination of the two methods is the generation of the electronic carpet plot, which will demonstrate the first-order-effects of various parameters such as the properties of the fibers and the matrix, manufacturing process, ply orientations, etc. The combined durability assessment method is being verified using the extensive durability database of NASA High Speed Research program as a part of the Accelerated Insertion of Materials – Composites program funded by DARPA. This research is a collaborative effort amongst several industry and academic partners. This program was developed under the guidance of Dr. Steve Wax and Dr. Leo Christodoulou of DARPA. It is under the technical direction of Dr. Ray Meilunas of NAVAIR.

KEYWORDS: accelerated testing, failure criteria, time-temperature superposition

INTRODUCTION

Accelerated Testing Methodology (ATM) is a systematic method of estimating the long-term performance of composite materials using series of tests at elevated temperatures [1,2]. The results are expressed as series of master curves capable of predicting the strength and life under wide ranges of loading conditions, temperature, and time to failure. The master curves generated by ATM are unique for each material and failure modes, and can serve as a material durability database. In order to include the effects of moisture, the new concept of temperature-moisture superposition [3] was used in the analysis.

Strain Invariant Failure Theory (SIFT) is a new failure criterion for composite materials that can predict initial and final failures of composite laminates and structures based on the information obtained from series of simple coupon tests [4,5]. In SIFT analysis, the complex failure modes of composite laminates and structures are evaluated at the constituent's level using detailed 3-D finite element analysis (FEA).

The advantages of combining the two methods are the following. ATM provides key information for performing durability analysis using SIFT; such as the modulus and critical values at temperature and loading conditions of interest. On the other hand, SIFT can relate the basic material durability properties to those of complex lamination and geometries, thus enhancing the applicability of the database and also reducing the number of tests required to generate the database [6].

The SIFT/ATM combined durability analysis is performed in the following steps as shown in Fig. 1. The first step is to perform the SIFT analysis at the static condition to obtain the critical strain invariants. The next step is to use the master curves generated by ATM to predict the resin modulus and the strengths at the load and environment conditions of interest. The micromechanics analysis predicts the 3-D ply properties based on the resin modulus, and the strain magnification factors used in the SIFT analysis. The SIFT analysis tailored for time-dependence is used to calculate the strain invariants within the fibers and the resin. The calculated strain invariants are then compared with the critical values to predict the long-term strength, or to predict the estimated lifetime. Using the linear cumulative damage law (LCD), the estimated life under combined fatigue/creep loads and also the residual strength after these loads can be analyzed.

Fig. 1: Outline of the Durability Analysis

ANALYSIS

In this section, the key analytical steps from Fig. 1 will be explained in details. These steps are the time-dependent failure analysis using SIFT, long-term strength prediction, life prediction, spectrum load, and residual strength prediction.

Time-Dependent Failure Analysis

SIFT was designed for the failure analysis at static condition, i.e. no time or fatigue effects, but can be extended to the durability analysis using the correspondence principle from the theory of viscoelasticity [7]. The correspondence principle suggests that the linear elastic analysis can be converted into a linear viscoelastic analysis, i.e. the time- and temperature-dependent analysis, by replacing the elastic moduli with the appropriate viscoelastic moduli such as the relaxation modulus or the reciprocal of the creep compliance.

First step is to calculate the critical strain invariants at the static condition using series of coupon test results performed at static condition. The critical values can also be calculated from the basic ply properties, though Gosse reports the importance to perform FEA of these coupon tests to obtain accurate values of the critical strain invariants. The calculated critical strain invariants are unique to the material, and also to the temperatures and the loading conditions of these coupon tests.

The next step is to perform similar analysis at the load and environment of interest. The master curves are used to predict the creep compliance of the resin, which is equivalent to the strain of the neat resin when unit stress is applied. Important parameter in this process is the reduced time to failure, which is a function of the temperature, moisture, and the duration of the load. The relation between these three parameters is based on the time-temperature superposition, and the newly proposed temperature-moisture superposition.

The change in the creep compliance of the resin is then translated to the changes in the 3-D ply properties using the micromechanical analysis. By using this modified 3-D ply properties, the 3-D strain states at the load and environment of interest can be calculated. Since it is not practical to analyze the complex viscoelastic behavior of the resin under fatigue loading, the creep compliance of equal load duration was used.

Once the maximum values of the strain invariants at the load and environment of interest are calculated, they are compared with the critical values at the same condition for the long-term strength and life predictions. These will be shown in the next section. Note that these strain invariant must be calculated separately for the applied mechanical load and thermal loads. The thermal load is due to the residual stress that builds up within the laminate during cure, and also due to the thermal expansion mismatch between the fiber and the resin.

Long-term Strength Prediction

The strength ratio is defined as the allowable load divided by the applied load. The concept of strength ratio as a scaling factor has been studied by many researchers including Tsai [8] and Manne [9]. When both the mechanical and thermal load are present, the strength ratio applies only to the applied mechanical load while the thermal load remains constant. Tsai has derived the equation for the strength ratio for Tsai-Wu failure criterion [8]. Here, the strength ratio for SIFT will be derived following the procedure outlined by Tsai.

The first strain invariant is defined as

$$J_1 = \varepsilon_I + \varepsilon_{II} + \varepsilon_{III} = \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3 \quad (1)$$

Where ε_i represent the normal strains, γ_{ij} represent the shear strains, the subscripts *I*, *II*, and *III* represent the three principal axes, and the subscripts 1, 2, and 3 represent arbitrary orthogonal axes. The first strain invariants J_1 are additive, meaning the mechanical and thermal components can be superposed. Therefore the strength ratio R_{J1} can be calculated using the critical value J_1^{cr} .

$$J_1^{cr} = R_{J1} J_1^M + J_1^T \quad (2)$$

$$R_{J1} = (J_1^{cr} - J_1^T) / J_1^M \quad (3)$$

The von Mises strain is defined as

$$\varepsilon_{vM}^2 = \{(\varepsilon_{II} - \varepsilon_{III})^2 + (\varepsilon_I - \varepsilon_{III})^2 + (\varepsilon_I - \varepsilon_{II})^2\} / 2 = J_1^2 - 3J_2 \quad (4)$$

where J_2 is the second strain invariant defined as

$$J_2 = \varepsilon_{II}\varepsilon_{III} + \varepsilon_I\varepsilon_{III} + \varepsilon_I\varepsilon_{II} = \varepsilon_2\varepsilon_3 + \varepsilon_1\varepsilon_3 + \varepsilon_1\varepsilon_2 - (\gamma_{23}^2 + \gamma_{13}^2 + \gamma_{12}^2) / 4 \quad (5)$$

The von Mises strains are not additive, i.e.

$$\varepsilon_{vM} \neq \varepsilon_{vM}^M + \varepsilon_{vM}^T \quad (6)$$

The strength ratio $R_{\varepsilon_{vM}}$ can be calculated by substituting the following strain components in Equation (4) and then equating with ε_{vM}^{cr} .

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_i &= R_{\varepsilon_{vM}} \varepsilon_i^M + \varepsilon_i^T \quad \text{where } i=1,2,3 \\ \gamma_{ij} &= R_{\varepsilon_{vM}} \gamma_{ij}^M + \gamma_{ij}^T \quad \text{where } i,j=1,2,3 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Solving the quadratic equation, the strength ratio can be calculated as

$$R_{\varepsilon VM} = -b/a + (b^2 - a c)^{1/2}/a \quad (8)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} a &= (\varepsilon_{VM}^M)^2 \\ b &= J_1^M J_1^T - 3J_2^{mix} \\ c &= (\varepsilon_{VM}^T)^2 - (\varepsilon_{VM}^{cr})^2 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} J_2^{mix} &= \{ \varepsilon_2^M \varepsilon_3^T + \varepsilon_2^T \varepsilon_3^M + \varepsilon_1^M \varepsilon_3^T + \varepsilon_1^T \varepsilon_3^M + \varepsilon_1^M \varepsilon_2^T + \varepsilon_1^T \varepsilon_2^M \} / 2 \\ &\quad - \{ \gamma_{23}^M \gamma_{23}^T + \gamma_{13}^M \gamma_{13}^T + \gamma_{12}^M \gamma_{12}^T \} / 4 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The equations above can be applied to both the static strength and the long-term strength, provided all the necessary critical values are known. The critical values for the long-term strength can be calculated from the master curves as follows. The discussion here will be limited to the single load case, i.e. when the temperature and the loading conditions remain constant for the whole duration of the loading. The multiple load case will be discussed later.

In the previous section, the resin compliance was calculated from the resin compliance master curve based on the reduced time to failure, which is a function of temperature, moisture, and the duration of the load. The critical values of the strain invariants are calculated from the respective master curves using the same parameter under the assumption that the relation between the temperature, moisture, and time are the same for any properties of the same material.

The failure modes used in the proposed analysis are (a) J_1 failure of the matrix, (b) ε_{VM} failure of the resin, (c) ε_{VM}^f failure of the fiber in tension, and (d) ε_{VM}^c failure of the fiber in compression. The critical values of (c) and (d) in the static condition can be related by a simple equation proposed by Gosse [10], but are separated here to show the difference in the long-term behaviors of the two failure modes.

The sets of master curves must be generated for all four failure modes, but once generated they can be used to predict the long-term performance of any type of laminates or structures. A complete set of master curves for a typical carbon/epoxy system was generated using many years worth of experimental results by Miyano *et al* [1,2,3]. Fig. 1 shows the normalized master curves for the four failure modes mentioned above.

Although the applicability of this database is technically limited to the material system tested, it can also provide insight into how similar material system will behave. For this purpose, the master curves are represented in non-dimensional form, normalized by the static value at room temperature, dry condition, and the time to failure of 1 minute. The long-term values of the critical strain invariants are calculated by multiplying these normalized values by the respective static values of the critical strain invariants from the previous section.

One set of master curves consists of static, creep, and several fatigue master curves. The vertical axis of the master curves is either the normalized constant strain rate strength (for static master curves) or the normalized applied load level (for creep and fatigue). The horizontal axis is the reduced time to failure, which is a function of the time to failure, temperature, and moisture. Each fatigue master curves represents certain number of cycles, such as $N_f=10$ cycles, 100cycles, and so on. The fatigue loads are typically represented by the mean load and the amplitude, or by the maximum load and the stress ratio R defined as minimum stress level over maximum stress level. For the fatigue master curves, the R is set to 0, and the maximum load level is plotted in the vertical axis. Note that the static master curve can be considered as a fatigue master curve of cycles to failure of $N_f= 1/2$ and $R=0$, and the creep master curve can be considered as a fatigue master curve of $R=1$. The maximum fatigue load for arbitrary stress ratio R can be calculated from the values from the creep master curve ($R=1$)

and the fatigue master curve ($R=0$) at appropriate cycles to failure N_f . Miyano proposed using a linear interpolation, and has produced experimental results to validate this assumption [1,2]. The maximum fatigue load for arbitrary cycles to failure N_f is calculated by the interpolation in logarithmic.

Fig. 2 shows the schematic of the long-term strength prediction at the reduced time to failure $t_{red} = 10^7 \text{ min}$, cycles to failure $N_f = 10^4$, and arbitrary stress ratio R . The reduced time to failure of 10^7 min corresponds to time to failure of $10^7 \text{ min} = 19 \text{ years}$ at room temperature dry condition, or $10^{7-4.52} \text{ min} = 5 \text{ hours}$ at hot wet condition of 50°C and 0.5% moisture content.

Fig. 2: Long-term strength prediction

The strength cannot be predicted when the reduced time to failure is outside the ranges of the master curves, or when the cycles to failure exceeds those of the fatigue master curves.

Life Prediction

In the previous section, the master curves were used to predict the allowable load level for the reduced time to failure of interest. The master curves can also be used to estimate life (time to failure) for the fixed load level. The procedure is similar to that explained in the previous section, but with few differences which will be explained next.

First issue is the strain analysis. The time to failure is predetermined in the strength prediction, but is not known *a priori* for the life prediction. Since it is not practical to perform iterative calculations for each of the four failure modes, the strain states at the intended time to failure is used. This is the same as the strain analysis used in the long-term strength prediction. The simplified strain-state will be “exact” when the intended time to failure is close to the predicted time to failure, or in other words, when it matter the most.

Second issue is the load frequencies. When the time to failure is not known, neither are the cycles to failure. On the other hand, most fatigue loads are applied in certain fixed frequencies, and therefore the frequencies can be used as one of the target parameters in which the fatigue master curves are scanned. By applying the time-temperature and moisture-temperature superpositions on the frequencies, a new parameter called the reduced frequencies can be calculated as

$$f_{red} = f_{T,M} \cdot a_{T,M}(T,M) \quad (11)$$

where $a_{T,M}(T,M)$ is called the shift factor, and is a function of the temperature and moisture of interest and those at the reference conditions.

Fig. 3 shows the schematic of the life prediction. First, the applied load level is plotted in the figure as a horizontal line, and the times to failure are calculated from each of the master curves. Since each fatigue master curve represents fixed cycles to failure, the effective frequencies at each of these intersections can be calculated. Using a linear interpolation in logarithmic, the time to failure for the target reduced frequencies can be calculated. The static master curve will have the lowest load frequencies, which will be used as the lower limit. The time to failure from the static master curve is used when the target frequencies is lower than this limit.

Fig. 3: Life prediction

The time to failure cannot be predicted when the applied load level or the target frequencies are higher than those for the master curves. If the load level is lower than that of the master curves, the maximum value of the time to failure from the master curves can be used as a conservative approximation.

The estimated lifetime is defined as the time to failure divided by the intended load duration. The estimated lifetime below unity implies that this material will not survive its' intended service life.

Spectrum Load

The load spectrum is defined as combination of load segments with varying load levels and load durations. Although the amplitude may change, the components of the multi-axial load are kept at the fixed ratio such that the failure modes are the same for all the segments. Under this condition, the life under the load spectrum can be predicted using the linear cumulative damage law (LCD). LCD accumulates damage due to each load segment as fractions, and predicts failure when the sum of these fractions equals unity. The most well-known form of LCD is the Miner's Rule, which accumulates damages due to load cycles. When the master curves are used, the damages are accumulated using time. These two types of LCD are equivalent when the calculations are performed using correct frequencies. The major difference is that the LCD with respect to time allows the consideration of the damages due to the static and creep loads also. This is a unique feature of the durability analysis method presented in this paper.

The damage fraction of each load segment is defined as the load duration divided by the time to failure for each load segment. This is equal to the reciprocal of the lifetime defined in the previous section. The failure is predicted when the sum of the damage fractions equals unity or higher. When the sum is below unity, the estimated lifetime for the load spectrum can be defined as the reciprocal of the sum. Fig. 4 shows the example of the life prediction based on LCD.

The strength prediction for the load spectrum is a difficult problem since there are no methods similar to the LCD to calculate the overall strength from multiple loads. One simplified method is to evaluate the strength for each load segment, and define the lowest strength as the overall strength under the load spectrum. This method yields reasonable results provided the lowest strength value is significantly lower than the other values, implying that the other segments have negligible effects to the overall strength.

Residual Strength Prediction

The residual strength after a single or multiple loads with the same failure modes can be calculated using the framework presented in this paper. The LCD and the static master curve are the key elements used in this prediction.

The first step is to calculate the damage fraction λ defined as the duration of the load divided by the time to failure. This can be from a single load, or from a load spectrum accumulated by LCD. The LCD states that this material can still withstand the load that will lead to the damage fraction if $1-\lambda$. The next step is to predict the load will lead to this amount of damage.

In the framework presented in this paper, typical “strength” refers to the constant-strain-rate (CSR) strength at a typical strain-rate defined in the test standard such as ASTM. Assuming the typical time to failure to be one minute, this static strength can be calculated from the static master curve. Miyano suggests that the CSR loading can be considered as many segments of creep loading with gradually increasing load levels. This relation is used for the calculation of the creep life from the static master curve, one of the unique capabilities of the ATM. Following equation was used in this calculation.

$$1 = \frac{\Delta t}{t_{c,1}} + \frac{\Delta t}{t_{c,2}} + \dots + \frac{\Delta t}{t_{c,n}} \quad (12)$$

where Δt is the load duration at each creep stress level and is defines as

$$\Delta t = \frac{t_{s,\lambda=0}}{n} = \frac{\sigma_{s,\lambda=0}}{(\sigma/t)n} \quad (13)$$

$t_{c,i}$ is the time to failure under increasing level of creep stress, and σ/t is the applied stress-rate proportional to the strain-rate.

When a prior damage represented as λ exists, the material will fail when the sum of Equation (12) reaches $1-\lambda$. This can be written as,

$$1 - \lambda = \frac{\Delta t_{\lambda}}{t_{c,\lambda,1}} + \frac{\Delta t_{\lambda}}{t_{c,\lambda,2}} + \dots + \frac{\Delta t_{\lambda}}{t_{c,\lambda,n}} \quad (14)$$

This is equivalent to the case where the stress-rate is reduced to $\sigma(1-\lambda)/t$, and the load duration of each segment is reduced to $\Delta t(1-\lambda)$ as shown in Fig. 4. This relation implies that the residual strength with prior damage of λ and the reduced time to failure t_{red} is equal to the static strength at $t_{red}/(1-\lambda)$. This can be written as

$$\sigma_{resid, \lambda, tf} = \sigma_{static, tf/(1-\lambda)} \quad (15)$$

This equation along with the monotonic decreasing static master curve predict the sudden death type residual strength often observed in composite materials [11].

Fig. 4: Residual strength calculation

RESULTS

Some results from the proposed durability analysis method are shown here. The material system analyzed is a typical carbon/epoxy system tested by Miyano and used to generate the master curves [1,2].

The best application of this method is for the first-order estimation of the effects of the various parameters on the durability performances. One method of presenting the result is known as the carpet plot, where the horizontal axis shows the percentages of $\pm 45^\circ$ plies, each curve shows different percentages of 0° plies, and the vertical axis shows the output of choice, typically strength and modulus.

Figs. 5 and 6 show the carpet plots created using this method. Fig. 5 is the conventional carpet plot with the vertical axis showing the final failure strength of the laminate at the applied unidirectional load. The result indicates that the 100% 0° ply is the best choice for this uni-directional load.

Fig. 5: Carpet plot of uni-directional strength

Fig. 6 shows another carpet plot vastly different from that of Fig. 5. The applied load is a combination of bi-axial normal and shear loads, and the output is the required thickness for the final

failure. The figure shows that the quasi-isotropic laminate fairs well, but there are other laminates such as “40/20/40” (indicates 40% 0° plies, 20% ±45° plies, and 40% 90° plies) performs better, i.e. requires less thickness.

Fig. 6: Carpet plot of required thickness under multi-axial load

Another method of visualizing the effects of the parameters is to plot several indicators of durability performance with respect to the parameters of interest. Fig. 7 shows one such example where the strength ratios for the initial and final failure are plotted with respect to combinations of temperature and moisture. The left end represents the room temperature dry condition (RTD) and the right end represents the hot wet condition (HTW). The result shows the reductions in initial and final strengths at HTW compared to RTD, but with varying degrees.

Fig. 7: Initial and final failure strength at various environments

CONCLUSIONS

Systematic analytical method for the accelerated durability assessment has been proposed. Details of the analytical process have been shown including a unique method of residual strength calculation based on the linear cumulative damage law. The derivation of the strength ratio for SIFT under combined mechanical and thermal loads were also shown. The proposed analytical method can predict the first order effect of the various parameters on the durability performance of the composite laminate. Three types of analyses were performed as examples, and their results were shown as carpet plots and as a regular chart.

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